

Mechanochemical Fluorescence Switching in Polymers containing Dithiomaleimide Moieties

Marc Karman,^a Ester Verde-Sesto,^{a,b} Christoph Weder,^{a,*} and Yoan C. Simon^{a,c,*}

^aAdolphe Merkle Institute, University of Fribourg, Chemin des Verdiers 4, 1700 Fribourg, Switzerland

^bPOLYMAT, University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU, Joxe Mari Korta Center, Avda. Tolosa 72, 20018 Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain

^cSchool of Polymer Science and Engineering, The University of Southern Mississippi, 118 College Dr. #5050 Hattiesburg 39406 MS USA

ABSTRACT: Polymers that display useful mechanochemical responses, such as changes of their fluorescence characteristics, are attracting great interest. Here, we introduce the fluorescent dithiomaleimide (DTM) motif as a mechanofluorophore and report the mechanoresponse of two polymer types containing this motif. Poly(methyl acrylate) (PMA) and poly(ϵ -caprolactone)s (PCL) featuring one DTM moiety in the center of each chain (PMA-DTM and PCL-DTM) were synthesized by controlled radical and coordination-insertion ring-opening polymerizations using bifunctional DTM-containing initiators. Upon ultrasonic treatment of PMA-DTM or PCL-DTM of sufficiently high initial molecular weight, both the molecular weight and the fluorescence intensity decreased with similar kinetics, while no significant fluorescence changes were observed for DTM-free reference polymers. The results show that the DTM motif can serve as a mechanophore that displays a mechanically induced fluorescence turn-off.

The exposure of polymers to excessive mechanical force usually elicits nonspecific and destructive chain scission, such mechanochemical events can be turned towards useful responses through the incorporation of specific stress-sensitive moieties, known as mechanophores. Their activation can in principle be achieved by stretching or compression of solid objects, but several aspects complicate a quantitative analysis of mechanochemical transduction in the solid state.¹⁻⁴ Initial investigations of novel mechanoresponsive polymers therefore frequently rely on monitoring chain scission upon exposure of dilute solutions to ultrasound.⁵⁻¹¹ This established approach has been applied to a range of mechanophores that serve as stress indicators,¹² mechanocatalyst,¹³ mechanoacid generators,¹⁴ among others.

Mechanochromic polymers, which change color upon application of mechanical force, are particularly useful as they allow for the convenient detection of mechanically induced damage without the need for complex equipment.^{12,15-20} While the mechanically induced (reversible) dissociation of fluorescent small molecule assemblies^{21,22} and metal complexes^{17,23,24} has long been known, there are fewer examples of mechanophore whose fluorescence characteristics can be reliably switched by mechanochemical modification of their covalent structure.^{15,25-31}

Here, we show that such materials can be accessed by incorporating fluorescent dithiomaleimides (DTM) as mechanophores. DTMs have been previously applied as protein marker³² and self-reporting fluorescent agents in

micelles.³³ O'Reilly and coworkers reported that a DTM derivative functionalized with two thiols exhibits intrinsic fluorescence, while the monothiomaleimide analogue is hardly fluorescent.³⁴ The fluorescence of DTM was further shown to depend on the substituent, which could readily be swapped through a thiol-exchange reaction.³⁵ In addition, the thioesters were shown to be activated in ultrasonication conditions thanks to a bond dissociation energy (ca. 71 kcal/mol) usually lower than that of C-C bonds (ca. 88 kcal/mol).^{36,37} We surmised that these features should make the DTM motif a compelling candidate for the design of polymers with mechanically switchable fluorescence characteristics. Poly(methyl acrylate)s (PMA) have widely been used to test new mechanophores,^{5,7,38-40} and we therefore elected to prepare PMAs with exactly one DTM moiety at the center of each chain. While the sonication-induced degradation of poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) has been studied,⁴¹ there have - to the best of authors' knowledge - been no ultrasonication studies of mechanophore-containing PCLs. Taking advantage of an available synthetic intermediate, we prepared DTM-containing PCLs of different M_n , and investigated their mechanochemical response. For all materials a preferred sonochemical chain scission of the DTM motif with concomitant fluorescence turn-off was observed (**Scheme 1a**). The results demonstrate the usefulness of DTM as a mechanofluorophore and suggest that other fluorescent mechanophores featuring C-S bonds are useful to visualize mechanochemical transduction events.

Scheme 1: (a) Schematic representation of the activation of DTM via ultrasound induced mechanical stress. (b) Synthesis of the *N*-benzyl-functionalized dibromomaleimide **1**, dithiomaleimide **2**, dithiomaleimide radical polymerization initiator **3**, DTM-containing PCL (PCL-DTM), and DTM-containing PMA (PMA-DTM), and structure of the reference polymers and compound **4**. i) K_2CO_3 , acetone, 18 h r.t., 74%; ii) imidazole, THF, 3 h r.t., 57%; iii) TEA, THF, overnight r.t., 78%; iv) $Sn(oct)_2$, overnight 110°C; v) $Cu(o)$, Me_6TREN , DMSO, 3 h r.t.

To enable the incorporation of the DTM motif into macromolecules, we adapted the synthetic strategy developed by Robin et al.³³ First, we carried out the nucleophilic substitution between the 2,3-dibromomaleimide and benzyl bromide (**Scheme 1b**) and obtained the *N*-benzyl-functionalized dibromomaleimide **1** in good yield (74%). The subsequent double addition-elimination reaction with mer-

captoethanol afforded 1-benzyl-3,4-bis(2-hydroxyethylthio)-*1H*-pyrrole-2,5-dione (**2**) in a yield of 57%. The esterification of **2** with α -bromoisobutyryl bromide yielded ((1-benzyl-2,5-dioxo-2,5-dihydro-*1H*-pyrrole-3,4-diyl)bis(sulfanediy))bis(ethane-2,1-diyl)bis(2-bromo-2-methylpropanoate) (**3**) in 79% yield. The mono-substituted maleimide 1-benzyl-3-((2-hydroxyethylthio)-*1H*-pyrrole-2,5-dione) (**4**) was also prepared to serve as reference. Compounds **1-4** served to elucidate the optical characteristics of the *N*-benzyl maleimide system. The UV-vis absorption spectra in 1,4-dioxane solutions are gradually red-shifted upon substitution of one (**4**) or two (**2-3**) bromides of **1** with thioether groups (**Figure 1a**). Steady-state fluorescence spectra in 1,4-dioxane reveal that the dithiomaleimides **2** and **3** exhibit bright green fluorescence, whereas both the dibromomaleimide **1** and the monothiomaleimide **4** do not show any appreciable emission (**Figure 1b**).

Figure 1: (a) UV-vis absorption spectra and (b) fluorescence spectra of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions of the respective compounds. The emission spectra were acquired with excitation λ_{ex} at the wavelength of maximum absorption λ_{abs} of each compound. The concentrations were $10^{-4} \text{ mol} \cdot L^{-1}$ for small molecules and $1.5 \text{ mg} \cdot mL^{-1}$ for the polymers.

Compound **3** was used as initiator for the reversible-deactivation radical polymerization of methyl acrylate. The polymerization was carried out in DMSO with a catalytic system composed of copper and tris[2-(dimethylamino)ethyl]amine (Me_6TREN) and afforded brightly green fluorescent polymers. By design, the polymer chains contain one DTM moiety at their center (**Scheme 1**). PMA was used

because it has been extensively studied and represents a well-understood platform.^{5,7,38-40,42} The number-average molecular weight, M_n , of the PMA-DTM synthesized here was controlled via the initiator:monomer ratio. Targeting an average chain length above the critical limit for chain scission (87 kg/mol),¹¹ PMA-DTM having a M_n of 106.6 kg/mol and dispersity (D) of 1.45 was synthesized (Table 1). In addition, a DTM-free PMA (107.2 kg/mol, $D = 1.13$) was used as a reference material. It is worth noting that the polymerization conditions were somewhat different for PMA and PMA-DTM, as they were grown from a mono- and a difunctional initiator, respectively, and that this affected the polymerization kinetics and ultimately the molecular weight distributions. DTM 2 was employed as the initiator for the ROP of ϵ -caprolactone. The polymerization was conducted in bulk at 110 °C with Sn(oct)₂ as a catalyst and brightly green fluorescent polymers were obtained. One may speculate that some reshuffling of the ester bonds by way of transesterification (and displacement of the DTM motifs away from the center) may occur, but the effect should be limited due to the use of Sn(oct)₂ as catalyst and the control of the conversion.^{43,44} PCL was chosen as a second system, as it was readily accessible from DTM 2 and only few reports describe PCL-centered mechanophores,⁴⁵ despite a broad application range of this polymer.⁴³ The critical limit has yet to be established for PCL; therefore polymers with M_n of 72.3 kg/mol (high- M_n PCL-DTM) and 18.1 kg/mol (low- M_n PCL-DTM) and D of 1.42 and 1.13 were prepared, speculating that these values are above and below the limit (Table 1). In this case a commercial DTM-free PCL (38.9 kg/mol, $D = 1.63$) was used as reference. In order to demonstrate the mechanoresponsive behavior of DTM, we first studied the behavior of DTM-PMA, where the placement of the mechanophores at the center of each chain is unequivocal. Thus, dilute solutions of the polymers in 1,4-dioxane were subjected to pulsed ultrasound (10.4 Wm⁻²) at an internal temperature of 20-22 °C for up to 5 hours. In order to monitor the effect of sonication as a function of time, aliquots were taken throughout the course of the experiment and each sample was characterized by size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) and fluorescence spectroscopy. All experiments were done in triplicate.

Table 1: Molecular weights of polymers studied.

Polymer	M_n (kg/mol) ^a	M_w (kg/mol) ^a	D^a
PMA-DTM	106.6	154.6	1.45
PMA	107.2	121.9	1.13
Low- M_n PCL-DTM	18.1	20.5	1.13
High- M_n PCL-DTM	72.3	104.9	1.42
PCL	41.3	63.6	1.54

^aDetermined by size exclusion chromatography (SEC).

Figure 2: (a) Representative size-exclusion chromatograms (refractive index signals) of PMA-DTM upon ultrasonication of a dilute polymer solution for the times indicated. (b) Evolution of $M_n/M_{n,0}$ upon ultrasonication of dilute solutions of

PMA-DTM, and a mixture of DTM-free PMA and **3**. (c) Evolution of the normalized fluorescence emission intensity at 525 nm upon ultrasonication of dilute solutions of PMA-DTM and a mixture of DTM-free PMA and **3**. The inset shows a picture of PMA-DTM solutions before and after sonication (picture taken under 365 nm UV light). (d) Representative fluorescence emission spectra of PMA-DTM upon ultrasonication of a dilute polymer solution for the times indicated. Solutions were prepared in 1,4-dioxane and the concentrations for the different polymers and for **3** were $c = 0.75 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ and $c = 7.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. The spectra were measured with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405 \text{ nm}$ and normalized to the initial intensity at $t = 0 \text{ min}$ for each sample. Data points are averages of three experiments.

Whereas the SEC traces of narrowly dispersed samples change to a bimodal molecular weight distribution upon ultrasonication (with a time-dependent decrease of the intensity of the peak associated with the original molecular weight and the appearance of a peak associated with chains of half the initial molecular weight),¹⁰ the SEC chromatograms of PMA-DTM show a gradual increase in elution time, indicating the characteristic molecular weight reduction for broader distributions (Figure 2a). The UV signal intensity recorded in the size-exclusion chromatograms also decreased, which is indicative of chemical changes to the DTM motif (Figure S22). A normalized plot of the ratio of M_n and the initial number-average molecular weight ($M_{n,0}$) against sonication time (Figure 2b, Figure S23) shows an exponential decay and a plateau at a $M_n/M_{n,0}$ ratio of $23\pm 1\%$ after $\sim 2 \text{ h}$ of sonication. The ultrasound-induced chain scission is accompanied by a corresponding decrease of the fluorescence emission intensity (Figure 2c,d), indicative of cleavage of the DTM motif. Indeed, a plot of the ratio of the fluorescence intensity and the initial fluorescence intensity against sonication time (Figure 2c, Figure S24) mirrors the observed decrease of M_n ; the trace levels off at $28\pm 7\%$ after 2 h . Thus, the data support the conclusion that the molecular-weight reduction is primarily related to the cleavage of the DTM motif (as opposed to random chain scission), although the small difference between $M_n/M_{n,0}$ and the relative fluorescence intensity suggests that some non-specific chain scission also occurs.

To confirm that the dissociation of the DTM motif in PMA-DTM is indeed induced via forces exerted on the macromolecules and not by side effects that may be generated during sonication, a 1,4-dioxane solution containing a mixture of the DTM-free reference PMA and reference compound **3** was subjected to ultrasound. The same conditions that caused chain scission and fluorescence decrease in the PMA-DTM solution were applied and the concentration of **3** was set to match the DTM content in the latter. The SEC data reveal that the molecular-weight reduction in the PMA reference, caused by unspecific chain scission, is significantly slower than in the case of PMA-DTM (Figure 2b, Figure S25, S26), indicating a lower activation barrier for chain scission in the latter. The chain scission rate constants (k) in the first hour of sonication were determined for both polymers with the method used by Lee *et al.* (Figure S27).⁴⁶ This analysis reveals a k_{PMA} of $2.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}\cdot\text{kDa}^{-1}$ for the control PMA, while the chain scission

rate for the DTM containing PMA was found to be two times higher ($k_{\text{PMA-DTM}} = 4.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}\cdot\text{kDa}^{-1}$). Even if the difference in D between the two polymers may also play a role, the twofold rate difference points out the influence of the insertion of the DTM motif in the center of the polymer backbone. While an M_n decrease of the reference polymer was observed, the fluorescence intensity of **3** remained unchanged when the compound was ultrasonicated in the presence of reference PMA for 5 hours (Figure 2c, Figure S28, S29). This particular result supports the conclusion that the decrease of the DTM fluorescence observed upon sonicating PMA-DTM is neither thermally activated nor induced by chemical species generated during sonication, but rather the result of mechanically induced cleavage, likely of the weak C-S bond, which is preferred over random chain cleavage events. Unfortunately, the identification of the scission product was neither possible by UV-vis absorption (Figure S30) nor by ¹H NMR spectroscopy (Figure S31).

High- M_n PCL-DTM was exposed as well to pulsed ultrasound, using the same conditions as for the PMAs. Also in this case, ultrasonication induced a reduction of M_n , as evidenced by the transition of the SEC peak to longer elution times (Figure 3a). A plot of $M_n/M_{n,0}$ reveals a decrease of M_n to $57\pm 2\%$ of the initial value (Figure 3b, Figure S32). The fluorescence emission spectrum for the different time also revealed a decrease in intensity (Figure 3d) upon sonication and a plot of the ratio of the fluorescence intensity and the initial fluorescence intensity against sonication time (Figure 3c, Figure S33) shows an exponential decrease to a plateau of $41\pm 8\%$. At the same time, the magnitude of the SEC UV absorbance signal (recorded at 405 nm) decreased (Figure S34). Thus, the optical changes again indicate a chemical modification of the DTM residue upon sonication, likely due to cleavage of the C-S bond. As expected, the M_n of the low- M_n PCL-DTM only experienced a minor ($6\pm 5\%$) reduction upon sonication (Figure 3b, Figure S35). The appearance of a shoulder in the low-molecular-weight range of the SEC chromatograms (Figure S36) suggests that a small fraction of the macromolecules had an initial $M_{n,0}$ above the cutoff molecular weight, which we qualitatively estimate to be around $15 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, and could be cleaved. Consistent with this observation, a small decrease of the fluorescence emission intensity ($-17\pm 5\%$) was observed after 5 h of sonication (Figure 3c, Figure S37, S38).

Also in this case we conducted control experiments and sonicated a non-covalent mixture of the reference PCL and **2**. The DTM-free PCL exhibits the expected decrease of M_n (Figure 3b, Figure S39, S40) to $66\pm 1\%$ of $M_{n,0}$ upon exposure to ultrasound. The determination of k for these polymers (Figure S41) revealed a value of 9.3×10^{-5} for the control PCL and 9.6×10^{-5} for the DTM containing PCL. The similarity of these two values is likely due to the presence of ester bonds in the backbone of the polymer, which represent a competitive weak motif that is present in a much higher concentration than DTM. Meanwhile, the fluorescence intensity associated with **2** is stable over the course of the experiment ($-2\pm 2\%$, Figure 3c, Figure S42, S43)

indicative for its non sensitivity to sonication conditions. Therefore, the conclusions drawn for the PMA system are also valid in the case of the PCL, as **2** was not activated by the sonication condition unless it has been covalently inserted into the polymer backbone.

Figure 3: (a) Representative size-exclusion chromatograms (refractive index signals) of high- M_n PCL-DTM upon ultrasonication of a dilute polymer solution for the times indicated. (b) Evolution of $M_n/M_{n,0}$ upon ultrasonication of dilute solution

of high- M_n PCL-DTM, low- M_n PCL-DTM, a mixture of DTM-free PCL and **2**. (c) Evolution of the fluorescence emission intensity at 525 nm upon ultrasonication of dilute solutions of high- M_n PCL-DTM, low- M_n PCL-DTM, a mixture of DTM-free PCL and **2**, and **2**. The inset shows a picture of the high- M_n PCL-DTM solution before and after sonication (picture taken under 365 nm UV light). (d) Representative fluorescence emission spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405$ nm) of PMA-DTM upon ultrasonication of a dilute polymer solution for the times indicated. Solutions were prepared in 1,4-dioxane and the concentrations for the different polymers and for **2** were $c = 0.75$ mg·mL⁻¹ and $c = 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$ mol·L⁻¹. The spectra were measured with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405$ nm and normalized to the initial intensity at $t = 0$ min for each sample. Data points are averages of three different experiments.

In summary, we have shown that the fluorescent DTM motif can serve as a mechanofluorophore that is capable of reporting the mechanoresponse of different polymers containing this motif. Upon ultrasonic treatment of PMA-DTM or PCL-DTM, the M_n and the fluorescence intensity decrease traces mirror each other, suggesting a relatively selective cleavage of the mechanophore. A priori, the DTM moiety should hold great much potential for integration in other polymer matrices, thanks to its ease of synthesis, its convenient functionalization, and the possibility to monitor its irreversible scission in a quantitative manner by way of fluorescence spectroscopy. In addition a better understanding of the scission process would be of interest as other mechanofluorophore bearing C-S bond may be feasible.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at DOI: 10.1021/acsmacrolett.XXX. Experimental section including materials and methods, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra, mass spectroscopy, elemental analysis results, SEC and fluorescence data of sonication experiments.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

*E-mail: christoph.weder@unifr.ch; yoan.simon@usm.edu

ORCID

Marc Karman: 0000-0003-0744-7625

Christoph Weder: 0000-0001-7183-1790

Yoan C. Simon: 0000-0002-5235-6127

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank Michela Di Giannantonio for providing the reference PMA. The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) / ERC grant agreement n° [ERC-2011-AdG 291490-MERESPO]. This work was also partially supported by the Adolphe Merkle Foundation and the National Center of Competence in Research (NCCR) Bio-Inspired Materials, a research instrument of the Swiss National Science Foundation.

REFERENCES

- Gossweiler, G. R.; Hewage, G. B.; Soriano, G.; Wang, Q. M.; Welshofer, G. W.; Zhao, X. H.; Craig, S. L., Mechanochemical Activation of Covalent Bonds in Polymers with Full and Repeatable Macroscopic Shape Recovery, *ACS Macro Lett.* **2014**, *3*, 216-219.
- Schafer, C. G.; Gallei, M.; Zahn, J. T.; Engelhardt, J.; Hellmann, G. P.; Rehahn, M., Reversible Light-, Thermo-, and Mechano-Responsive Elastomeric Polymer Opal Films, *Chem. Mater.* **2013**, *25*, 2309-2318.
- Larsen, M. B.; Boydston, A. J., "Flex-activated" mechano-phores: using polymer mechanochemistry to direct bond bending activation, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 8189-8192.
- Lenhardt, J. M.; Black, A. L.; Beiermann, B. A.; Steinberg, B. D.; Rahman, F.; Samborski, T.; Elsakar, J.; Moore, J. S.; Sottos, N. R.; Craig, S. L., Characterizing the mechanochemically active domains in gem-dihalocyclopropanated polybutadiene under compression and tension, *J. Mater. Chem.* **2011**, *21*, 8454-8459.
- May, P. A.; Munaretto, N. F.; Hamoy, M. B.; Robb, M. J.; Moore, J. S., Is Molecular Weight or Degree of Polymerization a Better Descriptor of Ultrasound-Induced Mechanochemical Transduction?, *ACS Macro Lett.* **2016**, *5*, 177-180.
- Schaefer, M.; Icli, B.; Weder, C.; Lattuada, M.; Kilbinger, A. F. M.; Simon, Y. C., The Role of Mass and Length in the Sonochemistry of Polymers, *Macromolecules* **2016**, *49*, 1630-1636.
- Kean, Z. S.; Gossweiler, G. R.; Kouznetsova, T. B.; Hewage, G. B.; Craig, S. L., A coumarin dimer probe of mechanochemical scission efficiency in the sonochemical activation of chain-centered mechanophore polymers, *Chem. Commun.* **2015**, *51*, 9157-9160.
- Cravotto, G.; Gaudino, E. C.; Cintas, P., On the mechanochemical activation by ultrasound, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2013**, *42*, 7521-7534.
- Brantley, J. N.; Wiggins, K. M.; Bielawski, C. W., Polymer mechanochemistry: the design and study of mechanophores, *Polym. Int.* **2013**, *62*, 2-12.
- Berkowski, K. L.; Potisek, S. L.; Hickenboth, C. R.; Moore, J. S., Ultrasound-induced site-specific cleavage of azo-functionalized poly(ethylene glycol), *Macromolecules* **2005**, *38*, 8975-8978.
- Potisek, S. L.; Davis, D. A.; Sottos, N. R.; White, S. R.; Moore, J. S., Mechanophore-linked addition polymers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2007**, *129*, 13808-13809.
- O'Bryan, G.; Wong, B. M.; McElhanon, J. R., Stress sensing in polycaprolactone films via an embedded photochromic compound, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2010**, *2*, 1594-1600.
- Groote, R.; Jakobs, R. T. M.; Sijbesma, R. P., Mechano-catalysis: forcing latent catalysts into action, **2013**, *4*, 4846.
- Nagamani, C.; Liu, H.; Moore, J. S., Mechanogeneration of Acid from Oxime Sulfonates, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 2540-2543.
- Chen, Y.; Spiering, A. J.; Karthikeyan, S.; Peters, G. W.; Meijer, E. W.; Sijbesma, R. P., Mechanically induced chemiluminescence from polymers incorporating a 1,2-dioxetane unit in the main chain, *Nat. Chem.* **2012**, *4*, 559-562.
- Kingsbury, C. M.; May, P. A.; Davis, D. A.; White, S. R.; Moore, J. S.; Sottos, N. R., Shear activation of mechanophore-crosslinked polymers, *J. Mater. Chem.* **2011**, *21*, 8381-8388.
- Zhang, G.; Lu, J.; Sabat, M.; Fraser, C. L., Polymorphism and reversible mechanochromic luminescence for solid-state difluoroboron avobenzene, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, *132*, 2160-2162.
- Crenshaw, B. R.; Weder, C., Self-Assessing Photoluminescent Polyurethanes, *Macromolecules* **2006**, *39*, 9581-9589.
- Crenshaw, B. R.; Weder, C., Deformation-induced color changes in melt-processed photoluminescent polymer blends, *Chem. Mater.* **2003**, *15*, 4717-4724.

20. Imato, K.; Irie, A.; Kosuge, T.; Ohishi, T.; Nishihara, M.; Takahara, A.; Otsuka, H., Mechanophores with a reversible radical system and freezing-induced mechanochemistry in polymer solutions and gels, *Angew. Chem. Int., Int. Ed.* **2015**, *54*, 6168-6172.
21. Sagara, Y.; Yamane, S.; Mitani, M.; Weder, C.; Kato, T., Mechanoresponsive Luminescent Molecular Assemblies: An Emerging Class of Materials, *Adv. Mater.* **2016**, *28*, 1073-1095.
22. Pucci, A.; Ruggeri, G., Mechanochromic polymer blends, **2011**, *21*, 8282-8291.
23. Balkenende, D. W.; Coulibaly, S.; Balog, S.; Simon, Y. C.; Fiore, G. L.; Weder, C., Mechanochemistry with metallosupramolecular polymers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 10493-10498.
24. Baranyai, P.; Marsi, G.; Jobbagy, C.; Domjan, A.; Olah, L.; Deak, A., Mechano-induced reversible colour and luminescence switching of a gold(i)-diphosphine complex, *Dalton. Trans.* **2015**, *44*, 13455-13459.
25. Sumi, T.; Goseki, R.; Otsuka, H., Tetraarylsuccinonitriles as mechanochromophores to generate highly stable luminescent carbon-centered radicals, *Chem. Commun.* **2017**, *53*, 11885-11888.
26. Nofen, E. M.; Zimmer, N.; Dasgupta, A.; Gunckel, R.; Koo, B.; Chattopadhyay, A.; Dai, L. L., Stress-sensing thermoset polymer networks via grafted cinnamoyl/cyclobutane mechanophore units in epoxy, *Polym. Chem.-Uk* **2016**, *7*, 7249-7259.
27. Li, Z.; Toivola, R.; Ding, F.; Yang, J.; Lai, P. N.; Howie, T.; Georgeson, G.; Jang, S. H.; Li, X.; Flinn, B. D.; Jen, A. K., Highly Sensitive Built-In Strain Sensors for Polymer Composites: Fluorescence Turn-On Response through Mechanochemical Activation, *Adv. Mater.* **2016**, *28*, 6592-6597.
28. Gostl, R.; Sijbesma, R. P., pi-extended anthracenes as sensitive probes for mechanical stress, *Chem. Sci.* **2016**, *7*, 370-375.
29. Wang, Z.; Ma, Z.; Wang, Y.; Xu, Z.; Luo, Y.; Wei, Y.; Jia, X., A Novel Mechanochromic and Photochromic Polymer Film: When Rhodamine Joins Polyurethane, *Adv. Mater.* **2015**, *27*, 6469-6474.
30. Davis, D. A.; Hamilton, A.; Yang, J.; Cremer, L. D.; Van Gough, D.; Potisek, S. L.; Ong, M. T.; Braun, P. V.; Martinez, T. J.; White, S. R.; Moore, J. S.; Sottos, N. R., Force-induced activation of covalent bonds in mechanoresponsive polymeric materials, *Nature* **2009**, *459*, 68-72.
31. Karman, M.; Verde-Sesto, E.; Weder, C., Mechanochemical Activation of Polymer-Embedded Photoluminescent Benzoxazole Moieties, **2018**, 1028-1033.
32. Robin, M. P.; Wilson, P.; Mabire, A. B.; Kiviaho, J. K.; Raymond, J. E.; Haddleton, D. M.; O'Reilly, R. K., Conjugation-induced fluorescent labeling of proteins and polymers using dithiomaleimides, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 2875-2878.
33. Robin, M. P.; Mabire, A. B.; Damborsky, J. C.; Thom, E. S.; Winzer-Serhan, U. H.; Raymond, J. E.; O'Reilly, R. K., New functional handle for use as a self-reporting contrast and delivery agent in nanomedicine, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 9518-9524.
34. Mabire, A. B.; Robin, M. P.; Quan, W. D.; Willcock, H.; Stavros, V. G.; O'Reilly, R. K., Aminomaleimide fluorophores: a simple functional group with bright, solvent dependent emission, *Chem. Commun.* **2015**, *51*, 9733-9736.
35. Robin, M. P.; O'Reilly, R. K., Fluorescent and chemico-fluorescent responsive polymers from dithiomaleimide and dibromomaleimide functional monomers, *Chem Sci* **2014**, *5*, 2717-2723.
36. Luo, Y.-R., *Comprehensive Handbook of Chemical Bond Energies*. CRC Press Taylor and Francis group: 2007; p 1688.
37. Lee, B.; Niu, Z.; Wang, J.; Slebodnick, C.; Craig, S. L., Relative Mechanical Strengths of Weak Bonds in Sonochemical Polymer Mechanochemistry, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 10826-10832.
38. Duan, H. Y.; Wang, Y. X.; Wang, L. J.; Min, Y. Q.; Zhang, X. H.; Du, B. Y., An Investigation of the Selective Chain Scission at Centered Diels-Alder Mechanophore under Ultrasonication, *Macromolecules* **2017**, *50*, 1353-1361.
39. Kryger, M. J.; Munaretto, A. M.; Moore, J. S., Structure-mechanochemical activity relationships for cyclobutane mechanophores, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 18992-18998.
40. Kryger, M. J.; Ong, M. T.; Odom, S. A.; Sottos, N. R.; White, S. R.; Martinez, T. J.; Moore, J. S., Masked cyanoacrylates unveiled by mechanical force, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, *132*, 4558-4559.
41. Sivalingam, G.; Agarwal, N.; Madras, G., Distributed midpoint chain scission in ultrasonic degradation of polymers, *Aiche J* **2004**, *50*, 2258-2265.
42. Shiraki, T.; Diesendruck, C. E.; Moore, J. S., The mechanochemical production of phenyl cations through heterolytic bond scission, *Faraday Discuss.* **2014**, *170*, 385-394.
43. Labet, M.; Thielemans, W., Synthesis of polycaprolactone: a review, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2009**, *38*, 3484-3504.
44. Biela, T.; Kowalski, A.; Libiszowski, J.; Duda, A.; Penczek, S., Progress in polymerization of cyclic esters: Mechanisms and synthetic applications, *Macromol. Symp.* **2006**, *240*, 47-55.
45. Peterson, G. I.; Larsen, M. B.; Ganter, M. A.; Storti, D. W.; Boydston, A. J., 3D-printed mechanochromic materials, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2015**, *7*, 577-583.
46. Lee, B.; Niu, Z.; Craig, S. L., The Mechanical Strength of a Mechanical Bond: Sonochemical Polymer Mechanochemistry of Poly(catenane) Copolymers, *Angew. Chem. Int., Int. Ed.* **2016**, *55*, 13086-13089.

Table of Contents

